

CLASSIFICATION OF THE APPLICATION OF METHODS IN TEACHING SCIENCES

Djurayeva Nargiza Horkulovna

Lecturer at the non-state educational institution of the University of Economics
and Pedagogy (Uzbekistan)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8153346>

Annotation. This article is aimed at improving the acceptance of bodies and phenomena of nature under study by children, improving the correct formation of concepts in the course of Natural (SCIENCE) Sciences, highlighting their didactic unity, highlighting their didactic Unity, using methods and techniques in a complex way.

Keywords. Methods, methodological techniques, Natural (SCIENCE) Sciences, fragment, diafilm, diapositive, schema, complex.

Teaching methods should not be confused with methodological methods. The methodical technique is only one of the elements of the method, its integral part (showing visual aids, fragments from films, film, slides, using diagrams on the board, drawings, demonstrating experiments, showing one or another activity during practical work in the field). geography, in the preschool sphere, etc.).

The method and methodological techniques are closely related to each other. Their didactic unity lies in the fact that they can be transferred into each other. For example, experiments performed by students are a teaching method, a demonstration of an experiment by a teacher during a story is a methodological device. Showing a slide film by a teacher during a story is considered a methodological technique, and watching educational films can also be a teaching method. Methods and techniques are used comprehensively, they complement each other, serve to improve the perception of natural objects and phenomena studied by children, the correct formation of concepts in the course of natural science (SCIENCE).

Each type of method consists of submethods. The leading method of transferring knowledge to students is the living word of the teacher - the story. It is combined with reading textbooks, demonstrating objects, objects and phenomena, using teaching methods, asking questions to students, reading fiction, etc.

According to S.R. Zokhidov, the story depends on the personality of the teacher, therefore it has great potential. The teacher's story is a visual, emotional and coherent narrative. In the story, strictly following the sequence, the teacher uses

various methods and techniques of logical work (analysis, comparison, generalization), gives students an example of a correctly constructed statement [1].

In science lessons, it is used when talking about an event or incident in nature, the history of the greatest discoveries, the life of scientists (biography), the creative activity of people associated with the development and restoration of flora and fauna. In some cases, the teacher's story in the lesson, with its plot orientation and imagery, approaches simple scientific works. When telling the material, the teacher poses questions to the students in order to leave a vivid picture in their minds, awaken good feelings, and logically develop a complex thought [2].

According to Zh. Zh. Karbozova, storytelling is a type of narration in which specific facts, events, processes or actions are clearly and fluently told. The story is told on behalf of a witness (tourist, young naturalist, traveler, participant in the discovery, etc.). The description is used in the sequential description of the characteristics of existing bodies and phenomena (minerals, flora and fauna), the climate of a particular natural zone [2].

Characteristic - a form of description, which consists in listing the signs and characteristics of a body (thing) or phenomenon (characteristics of mountains, rivers, natural areas). An explanation is a form of utterance in which new concepts and terms are revealed, causal relationships, dependencies are established, that is, the logical nature of a particular phenomenon (for example, why the night is long and the day is short). In short, in the tundra, why day and night, the seasons alternate) is being clarified. Explanation is used in all lessons, often in combination with discussion [2].

An argument is a statement that presents a consistent sequence of rules and evidence that leads students to inferences and conclusions. This form of story is used when it is necessary to analyze the phenomenon under study (for example, the influence of climate on changes in flora and fauna, the properties of water, metal). The above types of stories are used in SCIENCE lessons in harmony with each other.

According to Sh. N. Mustafaev, no matter how the teacher describes the material of the lesson, the didactic meaning remains in the active provision of scientifically generalized knowledge to students. Any story meets the following didactic requirements:

- 1) scientific character and high idealism of the chosen material;
- 2) logical consistency and provability;

- 3) be clear, fluent and understandable to students;
- 4) the teacher should respond to the fact that his speech is descriptive and calculated.

In grades 1-2, the duration of the story should not exceed 5-8 minutes, and in grades 3-4 - 10-12 minutes. During the story, it is necessary to use didactic techniques that contribute to the activation of learning [3].

Inserting a proverb, interesting material or an episode of reading a book into the story. The teacher can start the story after or before reading the relevant article. The use of additional material enriches and concretizes the story. Proverbs, sayings and riddles used in the course of the story enrich the lesson and make it easier for students to assimilate the material presented.

References:

1. Zohidova S.R. Didactic opportunities for improving the processes of professional socialization of future primary school teachers. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. T.: 2019.
2. Karbozova Yu.Yu. Preparation for design and electronic educational resources: Ph.D. dis. ... candidate of pedagogical sciences. Monday, 2018. - 25 p.
3. Mustafaev Sh.N. Technology of ideological and aesthetic education of students in the context of globalization // Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy ... dis. Abstract. Samarkand, 2018. 48 p.

